

The Use of Prepositional Phrase Bundles in Turkish Student Essays: A Core Expression Analysis

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In recent years, corpus-linguistic methods have been extensively used to study the use of lexical bundles (LB) by L2 writers in terms of structure and discourse functions. Previous research has shown that non-native speakers use fewer LBs than their native counterparts, but little is known about the partial uses of LBs. It was argued that automated analyses may fail to detect attempted uses of LBs, which draws an inaccurate picture of the use of LBs in learner corpora. Therefore, Shin et al. (2018) developed a core expression analysis to investigate the errors found in learner corpora. Core expression analysis is a manual check of the phrases formed around a core word (e.g., one of is the core expression in the bundles is one of the and one of the most). To date, no study has investigated the use of preposition-based LBs in the Turkish context using a core expression approach. To address this gap, the present research investigates four-word preposition-based LBs in a learner corpus (191,253 words) of human-rated L2 English opinion essays (n= 691) produced by Turkish university students by using a modified version of core expression analysis. As an extension to Shin et al., this study uses the regex function of the Antconc tool (an NLP tool to retrieve n-grams) to account for LBs with two prepositions. In a corpus-based analysis, the present study aims to (a) compare LB productions of native (LOCNESS) and non-native writers using a log-likelihood test, (b) classify student errors and find the most common errors based on hit frequency (c) examine the effects of errors on writing performance through linear mixed-effect models. It can be assumed from the findings in the literature and the possible effect of L1 Turkish that English-speaking Turkish university students might frequently misuse preposition-based LBs.